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Analysis of the temporal structure of vehicle flow in cities and a potential application to noise pollution. --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>This paper first proposes a methodological approach for analysing the urban road traffic flow. It hypothesizes that the temporal structure of the flow through the streets of a city is sufficiently uniform to define a single variable to describe the temporal variability of the flow, in one-hour intervals, throughout the city. Data from 54 road traffic flow monitoring stations were collected on an hourly basis during 2019 in Madrid, Spain. Then, the mean hourly flow ratio (MHFR) was defined and considered to test the hypothesis. The analyses carried out allow to conclude that the variable defined is adequate to describe the hourly time structure of the flow of road traffic over the course of a year on the streets of the city studied. This result opens the possibility that the temporal variability of environmental variables related to road traffic flow could be studied by using a single independent variable, with an accuracy of one hour, and valid throughout the whole city. Noise pollution is a serious environmental problem that, in our cities, is closely related to vehicle traffic. Consequently, as an example of applicability of MHFR, a study of the relation between hourly equivalent sound level (LAeq,1h) and MHFR was carried out. To do this, data recorded hourly throughout 2019 by 31 noise level measurement stations in Madrid were considered. As a result of this study, highly statistically significant positive correlations were found between the MHFR variable and the data corresponding to each of the noise monitoring stations. These findings suggest that the MHFR variable can be used for appropriate decision making on urban road traffic management, meaning that it can contribute to reducing the impact on the population of noise pollution and other pollutants associated with the hourly variation of traffic flow.</p>

Hourly monitoring of urban road traffic flows

Method to analyse the temporal structure of vehicle flow

Definition of new variables based on hourly flow rates:

- ✓ $HFRS(i,j)$
- ✓ $MHFR(j)$

A potential application estimating noise pollution levels variability

1 **Analysis of the temporal structure of vehicle flow in cities and a potential**
2 **application to noise pollution.**

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10 **ABSTRACT**

11 This paper first proposes a methodological approach for analysing the urban road traffic
12 flow. It hypothesizes that the temporal structure of the flow through the streets of a city
13 is sufficiently uniform to define a single variable to describe the temporal variability of
14 the flow, in one-hour intervals, throughout the city. Data from 54 road traffic flow
15 monitoring stations were collected on an hourly basis during 2019 in Madrid, Spain.
16 Then, the mean hourly flow ratio (*MHFR*) was defined and considered to test the
17 hypothesis. The analyses carried out allow to conclude that the variable defined is
18 adequate to describe the hourly time structure of the flow of road traffic over the course
19 of a year on the streets of the city studied. This result opens the possibility that the
20 temporal variability of environmental variables related to road traffic flow could be
21 studied by using a single independent variable, with an accuracy of one hour, and valid
22 throughout the whole city. Noise pollution is a serious environmental problem that, in our
23 cities, is closely related to vehicle traffic. Consequently, as an example of applicability of

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MHFR, a study of the relation between hourly equivalent sound level ($L_{Aeq,1h}$) and *MHFR* was carried out. To do this, data recorded hourly throughout 2019 by 31 noise level measurement stations in Madrid were considered. As a result of this study, highly statistically significant positive correlations were found between the *MHFR* variable and the data corresponding to each of the noise monitoring stations. These findings suggest that the *MHFR* variable can be used for appropriate decision making on urban road traffic management, meaning that it can contribute to reducing the impact on the population of noise pollution and other pollutants associated with the hourly variation of traffic flow.

Keywords: urban traffic flow; temporal variation; monitoring network; road traffic noise; noise pollution; noise measurement.

1. INTRODUCTION

Urban road traffic management is a priority issue in large cities around the world, in view of its impact on various different aspects of life (Rojas-Rueda et al., 2012) (Serok et al., 2022) (Chen et al., 2022) (Kaddoura and Nagel, 2018) (Masek et al., 2016). The World Health Organisation (WHO) has reported that there is a need to design cities and transport systems that reduce the current reliance on cars (WHO, 2018b). Several of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) for the 2030 Agenda are related to traffic management, such as Target 11.2 of SDG Goal 11, which aims to provide access to safe, affordable, accessible and sustainable transport systems for all by improving road safety, and in particular by expanding public transport (WHO, 2017).

Careful planning of road traffic in cities is desirable because uncongested road traffic has positive effects on the economy, air pollution levels, human health and people's perception of adequate management by public authorities (Zhou et al., 2023) (Chen et al., 2022) (Levy et al., 2010) (Currie and Walker, 2011) (Schrank, D. and Lomax, T., 2009).

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48 One way of knowing the state of traffic in cities is based on the use of permanent traffic
49 flow monitoring stations on the streets (Barroso et al., 2020) (Wang et al., 2022) (Barrigón
50 Morillas et al., 2022) (Feng et al., 2022) (Fernández Llorca et al., 2021) (Bottero et al.,
51 2013). Urban road traffic flow often shows great variability in terms of both its spatial
52 and temporal aspects, due to the different characteristics of the streets of a city and the
53 different circumstances that may take place in each of them throughout a year (Soni et al.,
54 2022) (Peng et al., 2021) (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019). Hence, a detailed analysis of the
55 temporal and spatial variation in vehicle flow around the city could provide insight into
56 road traffic behaviour that could help in making traffic management decisions.

57 Urban road traffic leads to problems with environmental pollution, of which noise is one
58 of the most significant (WHO, 2018a). Research has linked road traffic noise to various
59 effects on human health and well-being, such as cardiovascular problems (Begou et al.,
60 2020) (Dzhambov and Dimitrova, 2018), sleep disturbance (Shamsipour et al., 2022)
61 (Sanok et al., 2022), irritability and startle (Montes González et al., 2023) (Ali and
62 Tamura, 2002), and annoyance (Zhang and Ma, 2022) (Preisendörfer et al., 2022). These
63 effects are closely related to people's rest during nighttime (Münzel et al., 2019) (Röösli
64 et al., 2019) (Evandt et al., 2017) (Di et al., 2019), but the impact of road traffic noise
65 during the day period is also significant in sensitive buildings such as schools and
66 hospitals (Shukla and Tandel, 2024) (Martínez-Vilavella et al., 2023) (de Lima Andrade
67 et al., 2021) (Montes-González et al., 2019) (Baquero and Higuera, 2020). Although
68 action plans based on the results of strategic noise mapping are known to be useful for
69 the mitigation of environmental noise (Paschalidou et al., 2019) (Barrigón Morillas et al.,
70 2021a) (Faulkner and Murphy, 2022), strategies based on the design of buildings and
71 urban environments can also contribute positively to reducing the exposure of the
72 population to noise in cities (Eggenschwiler et al., 2022) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2021b)

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73 (Echevarria Sanchez et al., 2016). Road traffic is usually considered as the main source
74 of noise in urban environments (EEA, 2020) and, of course, noise levels are dependent
75 on the flow of vehicles (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019). Also, to a lesser extent, other variables
76 related to the flow, such as the speed or type of flow, or related to its generation
77 mechanisms, such as temperature, also have an effect on the noise generated by traffic
78 (Del Pizzo et al., 2020) (Licitra et al., 2019) (Sánchez-Fernández et al., 2021) (Bühlmann
79 and Van Blokland, 2014) (Cho and Mun, 2008). In addition, depending on the distances
80 between the sound source and the measurement point, meteorological conditions may
81 affect the propagation of the sound wave (ISO-1996-2. ISO-9613-2). For this reason, it
82 may be of interest to study whether there is a temporal structure of the sound level
83 variability that can be considered uniform within a city (Prieto Gajardo et al., 2016)
84 (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2015). Different types of aspects can influence the spatial and
85 temporal variation in urban noise (Quintero et al., 2019) (Han et al., 2018) (Casey et al.,
86 2017) (Mehdi et al., 2011) (Seto et al., 2007) (Liu et al., 2020) (Dreger et al., 2019)
87 (Mueller et al., 2018) (Nega et al., 2013). In this context of urban management, the use
88 of permanent noise level monitoring systems is therefore becoming widespread in order
89 to know the actual noise situation in cities in a way that enables public administrators to
90 take effective action.

91 Based on vehicle flow data collected over a full year from the set of stations that comprise
92 the monitoring network of the city of Madrid, this study aims to analyse the temporal
93 structure of traffic flows in the city to find a single variable that can be representative of
94 the hourly variability in traffic flows across the city as a whole. A further aim is to study
95 the application of this variable to basic aspects of urban management, such as road traffic
96 noise pollution. The results found have confirmed the hypothesis put forward and the
97 applicability of the proposed variable.

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98 2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

99 2.1. Study area

100 In this study, the flows of road traffic and sound levels were recorded hourly throughout
101 2019 at monitoring stations distributed throughout Madrid, Spain. Madrid is a city located
102 in the central area of Spain, with a population of 3,280,782 people, which reaches a total
103 of 6,779,888 inhabitants when the wider metropolitan area is considered (INE, 2022). The
104 metropolitan area towns have a significant population size and important work and
105 service areas, such as industrial zones, office areas, hospitals, large shopping centres,
106 universities, etc., as well as the city's airport. This urban structure and the wide network
107 of circular and radial roads favour the generation of important traffic flows in every
108 direction within the metropolitan area.

109 To analyse the temporal and spatial variation in the flow of vehicles, this city has a road
110 traffic flow monitoring network with 60 fixed stations, of which 54 operated properly in
111 2019 (Fig. 1a) (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2022). In addition, given the concern over health
112 and quality of life, the city has a network of 31 class 1 (IEC 61672-1, 2013) fixed noise
113 level monitoring stations, located on different streets, with microphones fixed
114 approximately 4–6 m above the ground (Fig. 1a and Fig. 1b) (Montes González et al.,
115 2020). Due to the different purposes of the two networks, the devices for measuring noise
116 levels are not located at the same points as those monitoring the traffic flow.

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(b)

117 Fig. 1: a) Locations of monitoring stations for traffic flow and sound level throughout the
118 city of Madrid; b) a sound level measurement station in Manuel Becerra Square.

119 2.2. Road traffic flow analysis

120 A road traffic flow study was carried out in this paper to investigate whether any
121 uniformity could be found in the temporal structure of the vehicle flow throughout the
122 city. From experimental data collected on an hourly basis over one year ($365 \times 24 = 8760$)
123 h) by each of the 54 stations, let be a variable called the hourly flow per station ($HFS(i,j)$),
124 in the form of a matrix composed of the values of the flows at each station ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 54$)
125 in each hour ($j = 1, 2, \dots, 8760$) of the year.

126 A preliminary analysis of the data from the traffic flow stations was carried out in order
127 to eliminate from the subsequent calculations the periods in which the stations did not
128 operate properly, for various technical reasons or due to flow anomalies occurring in the
129 street under consideration. This process was carried out in two phases: firstly, data were

130 removed for periods in which the measurement station was not operating, and secondly,
131 data associated with technical or flow anomalies were excluded. The number and
132 proportion of data eliminated in each of these phases is indicated in the analysis of results
133 presented below. To illustrate the importance of flow anomalies in this study, the results
134 of analyses without and with the elimination of anomalies considered in phase 2 will be
135 given throughout the study.

136 At this point of the work, it is hypothesised that the temporal structure of the flow through
137 the streets of a city is sufficiently uniform to define a single variable that can describe the
138 temporal variability of the flow, in one-hour intervals, throughout the city.

139 To test this hypothesis, two variables were obtained from the valid data: annual flow per
140 station ($AFS(i)$) (Eq.1) and mean hourly flow per station ($MHFS(i)$) (Eq. 2), which took
141 values for each station ($i=1, 2, \dots, 54$) as shown below:

$$142 \quad AFS(i) = \sum_{j=1}^{8760} HFS(i, j) \quad (1)$$

$$143 \quad MHFS(i) = [\sum_{j=1}^{8760} HFS(i, j)]/n_h(i) \quad (2)$$

144 where $n_h(i)$ are the number of hours with valid data for station (i).

145 In order to be able to compare flow variability values between the different measurement
146 stations, a new matrix variable was calculated that comprised values for each station ($i=1,$
147 $2, \dots, 54$) and each hour ($j=1, 2, \dots, 8760$). The matrix variable hourly flow ratio per station
148 ($HFRS(i, j)$) was defined as in Eq. (3):

$$149 \quad HFRS(i, j) = HFS(i, j)/MHFS(i) \quad (3)$$

150 This allowed to determine the flow rate at each station, at each hour, normalised with
151 respect to the average flow at the station itself.

152 In relation to the defined variables, the hypothesis stated above implies that the values of
153 the variable $HFRS(i, j)$, at the different flow stations (i) at each of the different hours (j)
154 of the year, will show a variability such that their Mean Hourly Flow Ratio ($MHFR(j)$),

155 calculated for each hour of the year as the sum of the $HFRS(i,j)$ values for the 54 stations
156 divided by the number of stations with valid data for hour (j), n_h , as shown in Eq. (4):

$$157 \quad MHFR(j) = \left[\sum_{i=1}^{54} HFRS(i,j) \right] / n_h(j) \quad (4)$$

158 and that this can be considered representative of the value of the flow ratio at each station
159 (i) at each hour of the year (j).

160 Two phases were proposed to verify this hypothesis, each of which was related to the
161 deductive process implicit in its analysis. In the first phase, an analysis of the hourly
162 variability of the variable $HFRS(i,j)$ was conducted based on its standard deviation
163 $DHFR(j)$, as shown in Eq. (5), and its mean value.

$$164 \quad DHFR(j) = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^{54} (HFRS(i,j) - MHFR(j))^2 / (n \vee s(i) - 1)} \quad (5)$$

165 In the second phase, an analysis of the representativeness of the variable $MHFR(j)$ with
166 respect to $HFRS(i,j)$ was carried out. For this purpose, a matrix variable called the relative
167 variation in hourly flow ratio per station ($RVHFRS$) was defined to determine the absolute
168 value of the relative variation in the variable $HFRS(i,j)$ with respect to the variable
169 $MHFR(j)$ for each station (i) and each hour of the year (j), as shown in Eq. (6):

$$170 \quad RVHFRS(i,j) = HFRS(i,j) - MHFR(j) \vee / MHFR(j) \quad (6)$$

172 An detailed analysis was then performed based on the mean value and standard deviation
173 of $RVHFRS(i,j)$ for each hour.

174 **2.3. Analysis of the relationship between vehicle flow and noise pollution**

175 To verify the practical usefulness of the $MHFR(j)$ variable, an extensive study was carried
176 out in which the capacity of this variable to explain the variability of urban noise in the
177 city of Madrid was analysed for all the sound level measurement stations with valid data.

178 With this in mind, the hourly equivalent sound level ($L_{Aeq,1h}$) recorded at each of the 31
179 fixed noise monitoring stations throughout the city of Madrid was considered. When
180 anomalous sound data caused by a malfunction of the monitoring station were detected,
181 they were eliminated. Anomalous noise data were also discarded from the analysis when
182 their value was below a minimum threshold of 35 dB, which was considered to be a
183 sufficiently low environmental noise threshold for the outdoor urban environments of the
184 city of Madrid.

185 A linear regression analysis was performed to analyse the relation between $L_{Aeq,1h}$ at each
186 of the 31 noise level monitoring stations and the matrix variable $MHFR(j)$. The coefficient
187 of determination (R^2) was calculated, and the significance of the relation between the two
188 variables was then determined using an F-test. This parametric test was carried out given
189 the large data size of each group ($N \approx 8760$) and the potential of parametric tests (Bárány
190 and Vu, 2007; Thatcher and Lubar, 2009).

191 **3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

192 **3.1. Road traffic flow analysis**

193 **3.1.1. Detection of anomalous flow data**

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195 An analysis of the 473,040 hourly traffic flow (HFS) data collected at the 54
196 monitoring stations over one year was initially carried out to detect possible outliers due
197 to different potential causes such as operational failure of a station, abrupt variations in
198 traffic due to temporary disruptions in the street or in nearby streets, etc. Null values were
199 detected for certain specific days, or for series of days, in one or both traffic directions.
200 These values have been removed from the subsequent calculations. Since it was not
201 possible to know whether the null values were due to station failure or traffic disruptions
202 in these time periods, it was considered necessary to remove the values for the hours
203 immediately before and after these null values. Street shutdown is a process that takes

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204 time, and does not necessarily start at the hour with a null value. The total number of data
205 samples removed based on this criterion was 5,316, representing 1.12 % of the total
206 number of 473,040 data samples initially collected. The average number of data samples
207 removed per station was 98.

208 A second data check was carried out with the aim of detecting other possible anomalous
209 data. Two criteria were used to identify the anomalous data, based on the assumption that
210 they represented variations in the profile of each station rather than repeated events over
211 a large number of stations. The criteria were: a) occasional values that significantly
212 exceeded the horizontal line of maximum values over the hours of the year or were below
213 the horizontal line of minima over the hours of the year; and b) increases and decreases
214 in hourly flow over a sequence of days or weeks with respect to the temporal structure of
215 the annual flow profile. As an example, Fig. 2 shows the annual evolution of the hourly
216 flow ($HFS(i,j)$) for monitoring stations 4 (Fig. 2a) and 8 (Fig. 2b). Two types of flow
217 variations can be observed in these figures. Firstly, those that are repeated throughout the
218 set of measuring stations and which, in principle, correspond to normal events occurring
219 in the city. Secondly, anomalies specific to a particular station related to many events that
220 occur in urban streets (maintenance works, temporal markets streets, parades, etc). In the
221 first type, it can be observed an expected dip in the MHFR between the hours 5000 and
222 6000, which coincides with the month of August. This is a summer holiday period in
223 which Madrid and many others cities in Spain usually experiences a large reduction in
224 the flow of vehicles as many residents move to other regions of the country. Concerning
225 the second type, anomalous increases in flow can be seen at station 4 between hours 2800
226 and 2900 and around hour 5300 (Fig. 2a), and at station 8 around the hours 1000, 2500,
227 5500 and 7000 (Fig. 2b). Anomalous decreases in the flow can also be seen in Fig. 2b
228 around hours 1500, 4500 and 6000, as well as a continuous decrease in flow between

229 hours 500 and 900. The total number of anomalous data samples from the 54 stations that
230 were excluded based on criteria a) and b) was 5,955, representing 1.26 % of the total
231 number of 473,040 data samples initially collected.

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232 Fig. 2. Annual evolution of the hourly value of the vehicle flow (HFS) at two
 233 monitoring stations: a) station 4; b) station 8.

234 The mean hourly vehicle flow value at each station ($MHFS(i)$) was then calculated
 235 by dividing the annual flow of the station ($AFS(i)$), calculated as the sum of the hourly
 236 flows for each station ($HFS(i,j)$), by the number of hours for which the data were
 237 considered valid. Fig. 3 shows the values of $MHFS(i)$ obtained for each traffic flow
 238 station, with anomalous data included (orange bars) and excluded following criteria a)
 239 and b) as explained above (blue bars). It can be seen that there are practically no
 240 differences in $MHFS(i)$. Given the volume of data at each station, the values removed
 241 based on criteria a) and b) can be seen to make up a very small fraction of the total, and
 242 therefore have no significant influence.

243
 244 Fig. 3. Mean hourly vehicle flow for each station ($MHFS(i)$), with and without removal
 245 of anomalous data.

246 In view of the large variability in mean hourly flow between the different stations
 247 considered in the study (between approximately 250 and 12,700 vehicles/h), it is logical
 248 to think that, if it is desired to derive a value that can be representative of all the stations,
 249 it is not possible to use the net flow; instead, it would be necessary to apply some kind of
 250 normalisation. For this reason, the hourly flow ratio for each station ($HFRS(i,j)$) was
 251 calculated with respect to the mean hourly vehicle flow at the station ($MHFS(i)$). That is,

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252 the hourly flow value of the station ($HFS(i,j)$) was divided by $MHFS(i)$, as shown in Eq.
253 (3). This was done by both including the anomalous values (giving 467,975 data samples)
254 and by applying exclusion criteria a) and b) (leaving 461,768 data samples).

255 **3.1.2. Hypothesis testing**

256 Once the $HFRS(i,j)$ matrix variable was calculated for each of the station (i), the
257 hypothesis of uniformity or stability in the values of $HFRS(i,j)$ throughout the different
258 flow stations was raised. Consequently, the possibility is considered of obtaining a single
259 value for the flow ratio corresponding to each hour (j), which was representative of that
260 hour and was valid for all the stations in the city of Madrid. Hence, for each hour of the
261 year, the mean flow ratio for that hour ($MHFR(j)$) was calculated by dividing the sum of
262 the $HFRS(i,j)$ values for the 54 stations for each hour by the number of stations with data
263 for that hour, as shown in Eq. (4). A total of 8,760 data were calculated for $MHFR(j)$. Fig.
264 4 shows a plot of the $MHFR(j)$ variable with respect to the hours of the year, both
265 including anomalous data (Fig. 4a) and excluding them based on criteria a) and b) (Fig.
266 4b). Although the overall structure is very similar in both cases, some differences in the
267 maximum values can be observed between the two figures, as expected.

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268 Fig. 4. Mean hourly flow ratio ($MHFR(j)$) values: a) including anomalous data; b)
269 excluding anomalous data.

270 Different analyses were then carried out with the aim of analysing whether the hypothesis
271 that the values of the $HFRS(i,j)$ variable could be considered stable, and hence whether
272 there was a single value (the matrix variable $MHFR(j)$) that was representative of the flow
273 ratio for each hour of the year and that was valid for all the flow stations in Madrid,
274 regardless of the different types of street and traffic flow.

275 In the first phase, to verify the hypothesis, an initial analysis was carried out by calculating
276 the standard deviation of $HFRS(i,j)$ for each hour (j). This variable is referred to as
277 $DHFR(j)$ in Eq. (5). The mean values of the matrix variable $DHFR(j)$, both including and
278 excluding anomalous data, were 0.236 and 0.252 respectively, and its standard deviation
279 was 0.110 and 0.126. These mean values can be considered very reasonable and are
280 significantly below one, which was the mean value of the $MHFR(j)$ variable. Furthermore,
281 the value of the standard deviation was clearly lower than the mean value of the $DHFR(j)$
282 variable, indicating strong stability in the values of the standard deviation for the different
283 hours of the year. These results provide a first indication that the values of $MHFR(j)$ can
284 be considered representative of the values of the $HFRS(i,j)$ variable, which are specific to
285 each station. However, a detailed analysis of the behaviour of the standard deviation with
286 respect to the mean values was required so that this variable could be analysed not only
287 globally, but on an hourly basis, as shown below.

288 To analyse the relative significance of the $DHFR(j)$ variable with respect to the $MHFR(j)$
289 variable for the different hours of the year, the ratio between $DHFR(j)$ and $MHFR(j)$ was
290 determined for each hour. For a more detailed analysis of the behaviour of this matrix
291 variable over time, the number of hours in which the *ratio* was greater than one (meaning
292 that $DHFR(j)$ was greater than $MHFR(j)$) was calculated. As a result, it was found that

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293 $DHFR(j)$ was greater than $MHFR(j)$ in only 21 hours (when anomalous data were
294 included), and 9 hours (when anomalous data were removed). These values mean that,
295 with respect to the total hours of the year, $DHFR(j)$ is greater than $MHFR(j)$ in only 0.24 %
296 or 0.10 % of the hours. These results give an idea of the stability of the values of the
297 $HFRS(i,j)$ variable across the different measurement stations for each of the hours of the
298 year, and lead to the conclusion that the values of the $MHFR(j)$ variable are representative
299 of the values for the set of the stations of the city and the hours of the year.

300 In the second phase of hypothesis verification, an approach was taken to further analyse
301 the representativeness of the $MHFR(j)$ variable with respect to $HFRS(i,j)$. To do this, the
302 significance of the differences between the two variables relative to $MHFR(j)$ was
303 analysed with $RVHFRS(i,j)$, as shown in Eq. (6), for both datasets, i.e., including the
304 anomalous data (467,975 samples) and excluding them (461,768 samples). Subsequently,
305 its mean value at each hour of the year ($MRVHFR(j)$) was obtained from the quotient
306 between $RVHFRS(i,j)$ and the number of stations with valid data (n_s) for that hour (j). This
307 matrix variable of 8,760 values was called the mean relative variation of the hourly flow
308 ratio ($MRVHFR(j)$). The mean values of this variable ($MMRVHFR$) including and
309 excluding outliers were 0.232 and 0.228, respectively, with a standard deviation
310 ($DMRVHFR$) of 0.135 in both cases. This means that on average, over 8,760 hours, the
311 difference between the $HFRS(i,j)$ and the mean of this variable per hour ($MHFR(j)$)
312 represented approximately 23% of the value of the mean ($MHFR(j)$). Finally, the standard
313 deviation in the relative variation in the flow proportions per hour ($DRVHFR(j)$) was
314 calculated. This matrix variable had mean values over 8,760 hours of 0.199 and 0.190
315 when anomalous data were included and excluded, respectively, and values for the
316 standard deviation of 0.140 and 0.132. The number of hours in which the value of
317 $DRVHFR(j)$ was higher than the value of $MRVHFR(j)$ was 988 when outliers were

	Mean	33.1	20.7	13.7	9.0	5.9	3.6	2.2	1.4	1.0	0.8
Excluding anomalous data	Deviation	10.7	13.5	12.2	10.0	7.5	5.0	3.2	2.2	1.7	1.4
	Maximum	54.0	49.0	42.0	37.0	33.0	26.0	19.0	12.0	9.0	8.0
	Minimum	4.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0

340 The first observation that can be made from Table 1 is that the variation in the results is
341 low when the cases including and excluding outliers are compared, which reveals the
342 small effect that the anomalous flow values have on the $MHFR(j)$ variable. It is quite
343 likely that this result is associated with the high level of detail with which the flow
344 analysis was performed in this study. Note that the analysis of flow variability was
345 performed on hourly basis. If, at most hours, most of the stations have a similar behaviour,
346 the weight of what happens at some stations or at some hours is not representative of the
347 values obtained for the $HFRS(i,j)$ variable.

348 It can also be observed that in any of the cases considered here, the average number of
349 stations with relative variations in the flow ratio of more than a factor of 0.6 (60%) was
350 less than four. Similarly, for a factor of one (>100%), the average number of stations was
351 less than one. This can be considered an important result that once again implies the
352 existence of strong uniformity in the road traffic flows in the city. Therefore, if there are
353 differences between the hourly behaviour of traffic flow according to the type of street,
354 the type of district to which it belongs or the land uses, these can be considered that,
355 evaluated over the whole year, they are not sufficiently important to representatively
356 affect the uniformity of the $HFRS(j)$ variable. Although previous research based on
357 Fourier analysis has found some stability in the temporal structure of environmental noise
358 in cities with different urban characteristics (Prieto Gajardo et al., 2016) (Barrigón
359 Morillas et al., 2015), and road traffic noise can be considered the main sound source in
360 urban environments (EEA, 2020), this uniformity in the temporal structure of urban road
361 traffic has not been previously reported, to the best of the authors' knowledge.

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362 The results presented here indicate that, by using a single variable, obtained from urban
363 networks for monitoring road traffic flows, it is possible to know the temporal and spatial
364 variation in vehicle flows throughout the city. This opens the possibility of studying other
365 variables that are directly influenced by road traffic, such as noise pollution or certain
366 types of air pollutants, with a temporal precision of one hour.

367 **3.2. Analysis of the dependence of road traffic noise level on $MHFR(j)$**

368 One urban environmental variable that is of great interest and which has a clear
369 dependence on urban traffic is noise pollution. The temporal variability in road traffic
370 flow in cities is an important factor in the temporal evolution of urban environmental
371 noise levels, which is taken into account in the production of dynamic noise maps
372 (Bescond et al., 2021) (Fredianelli et al., 2022) (Hong et al., 2023). Many prior studies of
373 environmental noise required a knowledge of the road traffic flow on the street under
374 investigation. To the best of the authors' knowledge, never in the scientific literature an
375 urban noise study was conducted for a wide noise level monitoring network distributed
376 over the whole city using a single variable. The objective in this section is to determine
377 the extent to which the new matrix variable $MHFR(j)$ can explain the variability in noise
378 levels throughout the city of Madrid.

379 It is well known that road traffic is the main cause of noise pollution in a city, both
380 spatially and temporally. But it is also true that there are other sources of noise pollution
381 and could occur that, in some streets, these other noise sources could be significant
382 enough so that traffic could not be considered the main source of noise pollution there.
383 Therefore, it may be valuable to be able to determine for a full year the relative significance
384 of hourly variability of road traffic on the hourly variability of noise pollution in a specific
385 urban location, given the presence of other noise sources and the importance of
386 differentiating between these noise sources for strategic noise mapping and for estimating

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387 the impact of each noise source on the health of residents. Therefore, for the objectives
388 of the work, it is important to study the relationships between flow and sound level
389 considering the temporal structure of the overall noise (which is what the sound level
390 meter measures); that is, all the sound sources that are usually present at each point
391 analysed must be considered.

392 If the objective of this section is achieved, and the new variable proposed in this paper
393 allows for a general study of the variation of noise in different locations, it would also
394 enable a study of the relative importance of road traffic with respect to the rest of the
395 noise sources in a given location.

396 A linear regression study was then carried out between the decimal logarithm of the
397 $MHFR(j)$ variable and the hourly values of the equivalent noise level ($L_{Aeq,1h}$) that were
398 collected at the different noise monitoring stations across the city of Madrid. Given the
399 aims of this study, all of the measuring stations in proper operating condition were
400 considered, regardless of their location and the noise sources that may have been most
401 significant at that site.

402 It was also considered of interest that this regression study was carried out by considering
403 the sound level data in two different ways. In the first analysis, no anomalous data from
404 the noise monitoring station were eliminated if it was not clear that the anomaly was
405 caused by a malfunction of the monitoring station. In the second analysis, the anomalous
406 noise data were eliminated. The aim of this double analysis was to check the stability of
407 the defined variable and the influence of the presence of anomalous data on its capacity
408 to explain the variability of the traffic-related variable. From the linear relationships
409 between $L_{Aeq,1h}$ and $MHFR(j)$, for the case where the anomalous values in the sound levels
410 were not eliminated, the proportion of hours missed was 4.72 % (12,818 hours) of the
411 total ($31 \times 8760 = 271,560$ h). The percentage of hours considered was therefore 95.28 %.

412 In the case where noise outliers were excluded, the percentage of missed hours was 5.78%
 413 (15,699 h). Hence, the anomalous values removed from the sound data represented only
 414 1.06 % (2,881 h) of the total number of 271,560 data samples. Table 2 shows the
 415 coefficient of determination (R^2) of the linear regression analysis between hourly noise
 416 levels ($L_{Aeq,1h}$) at each of the 31 sound level measurement stations and $MHFR(j)$, as well
 417 as a brief description of the main sound source at each location. This analysis was carried
 418 out for the following four cases:

- 419 • C1: excluding zero values in traffic flow data and values of zero and < 35 dB for
 420 sound levels.
- 421 • C2: excluding zero values and anomalous data for traffic flows and values of zero
 422 and < 35 dB for sound levels.
- 423 • C3: as for C1, but also excluding anomalous noise data.
- 424 • C4: as for C2, but also eliminating anomalous noise data.

425 Table 2. Coefficient of determination for a linear regression analysis between noise levels
 426 ($L_{Aeq,1h}$) at each of the 31 sound level measurement stations and $MHFR(j)$ for cases C1,
 427 C2, C3 and C4

No. noise station	Station name	Main sound source in the immediate surroundings	R^2			
			C1	C2	C3	C4
1	Paseo de Recoletos	Road traffic	0.40***	0.41***	0.50***	0.50***
2	Carlos V	Road traffic	0.59***	0.59***	0.62***	0.62***
3	Plaza del Carmen	People, bars and road traffic	0.16***	0.16***	0.16***	0.16***
4	Plaza de España	Road traffic	0.57***	0.57***	0.59***	0.60***
5	Barrio del Pilar	Road traffic	0.63***	0.63***	0.60***	0.61***
6	Gregorio Marañón	Road traffic	0.67***	0.67***	0.68***	0.68***
7	Escuelas Aguirres	Road traffic	0.61***	0.61***	0.62***	0.62***
8	Cuatro Caminos	Road traffic	0.67***	0.67***	0.68***	0.68***
9	Ramón y Cajal	Road traffic	0.71***	0.71***	0.71***	0.72***
10	Manuel Becerra	Road traffic	0.64***	0.64***	0.66***	0.66***
11	Vallecas	Road traffic	0.48***	0.48***	0.51***	0.51***
12	Fernández Ladreda	Road traffic	0.70***	0.70***	0.70***	0.70***

13	Arturo Soria	Road traffic	0.74 ^{***}	0.74 ^{***}	0.76 ^{***}	0.76 ^{***}
14	Villaverde	Road traffic	0.55 ^{***}	0.55 ^{***}	0.57 ^{***}	0.57 ^{***}
15	Farolillo	Road traffic	0.56 ^{***}	0.56 ^{***}	0.61 ^{***}	0.61 ^{***}
16	Alto Extremadura	Road traffic	0.45 ^{***}	0.45 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}
17	Avenida de Moratalaz	Road traffic	0.62 ^{***}	0.63 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}
18	Casa de Campo	People and nature	0.47 ^{***}	0.47 ^{***}	0.49 ^{***}	0.49 ^{***}
19	Santa Eugenia	Road traffic	0.73 ^{***}	0.73 ^{***}	0.78 ^{***}	0.78 ^{***}
20	Embajada	Road traffic	0.65 ^{***}	0.65 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}
21	Barajas Pueblo	Road and air traffic	0.73 ^{***}	0.73 ^{***}	0.75 ^{***}	0.75 ^{***}
22	Cuatro Vientos	Road traffic	0.86 ^{***}	0.86 ^{***}	0.86 ^{***}	0.86 ^{***}
23	El Pardo	Road traffic	0.75 ^{***}	0.75 ^{***}	0.79 ^{***}	0.79 ^{***}
24	Campo de las Naciones	Road traffic	0.70 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}	0.71 ^{***}
25	Sanchinarro	Road traffic	0.68 ^{***}	0.68 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}
26	Méndez Álvaro	Road ant train traffic	0.51 ^{***}	0.51 ^{***}	0.54 ^{***}	0.54 ^{***}
27	Castellana	Road traffic	0.65 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.67 ^{***}	0.67 ^{***}
28	Plaza de Castilla	Road traffic	0.62 ^{***}	0.63 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}	0.66 ^{***}
29	Ensanche de Vallecas	Road traffic	0.79 ^{***}	0.79 ^{***}	0.80 ^{***}	0.80 ^{***}
30	Urb. Embajada II	Road traffic	0.67 ^{***}	0.67 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}	0.69 ^{***}
31	Tres Olivos	Road traffic	0.78 ^{***}	0.78 ^{***}	0.80 ^{***}	0.80 ^{***}

428 *** Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.001$.

429 From Table 2, it can be seen that all the relationships between the noise indicator $L_{Aeq,1h}$
430 and $MHFR(j)$ were highly statistically significant ($p \leq 0.001$) for the 31 noise monitoring
431 stations in all four cases (C1, C2, C3 and C4) under study. Considering the different
432 ranges of p -values taken by the scientific community as statistically significant, the
433 strength of the correlation can be established for an $N=8760$ data (Fritz and MacKinnon,
434 2007) (Hulley et al., 2013): thus, for a p -value ≤ 0.001 (***) a very strong relationship
435 would be obtained with an $R \geq 0.066$ or R -squared ≥ 0.004 , values that are exceeded for
436 all the linear relationships established in each of the sound level measurement stations.
437 This result confirms that the proposed matrix variable $MHFR(j)$ can explain the variability
438 in the noise levels throughout the city of Madrid. Furthermore, the relationships found
439 here are highly statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) for all four assumptions analysed and
440 are, therefore, independent of the elimination of anomalies both in the traffic flows and
441 noise levels. It can be concluded that the basic objective of this section has been achieved,
442 that is, it has been shown that the new matrix variable $MHFR(j)$ can explain the variability

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443 in noise levels throughout the city of Madrid. It is relevant to point out that this occurs
444 even in those sound level measurement stations at which the closest or most important
445 main sound source is not road traffic. Likewise, these results allow to conclude that the
446 proposed methodology developed is useful for evaluating the relative importance of
447 traffic noise in relation to the rest of the sound sources at a given point in the city. Methods
448 to differentiate the contribution to urban noise from specific sources (in our case, road
449 traffic) are of great practical importance. For example, in the production of noise maps
450 and their verification. Differentiating the specific contribution of one noise source from
451 the rest is essential for the improvement of the health and quality of life of the citizen, as
452 it allows the planning of control measures and action plans focused on the contribution to
453 urban noise of that source independently. This will result in more effective measures and
454 more efficient public spending.

455 When this result is compared with those of previous works, it is important to note that the
456 $MHFR(j)$ matrix allowed to perform a correlation analysis with respect to $L_{Aeq,1h}$ for all
457 31 stations of the noise monitoring network in Madrid, whereas 10 of the 31 stations were
458 discarded in previous investigations of the relationship between $L_{Aeq,1h}$ and temperature
459 because they did not meet the requirement that road traffic was the predominant source,
460 or because there was a lack of data or a significant presence of anomalous sound events
461 for other reasons (Barrigón Morillas et al., 2022).

462 When the values for the coefficient of determination (R^2) from Table 2 are compared, a
463 slight increase in the explanation of noise level variability can be found in general terms
464 from case C1 to case C4. It is worth noting that the variation between columns C1 and
465 C2 is very small, as is the variation between cases C3 and C4, which reflects the little
466 influence of removing the anomalous traffic flow data. This reinforces the conclusion in
467 regard to the stability of the new matrix variable proposed in this manuscript. There seems

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468 to be a small increment in columns C3 and C4 with respect to cases C1 and C2, in which
469 the anomalous values of noise level are excluded from the regression analysis. A high
470 percentage of the explanation of the variability in $L_{Aeq,1h}$ at some noise monitoring stations
471 can be explained by the single variable $MHFR(j)$ related to road traffic flow, reaching a
472 maximum value of 86% at station 22 (Cuatro Vientos) in cases C1, C2, C3 and C4.
473 Barrigón Morillas et al. reported similar results from various investigations where the
474 correlation coefficient (R) between the logarithm of road traffic flow and environmental
475 noise level were around 0.8 for varying conditions in terms of the duration of the
476 measurement, the height of the microphone above the ground, the distance of the
477 microphone from the traffic lanes, and the method used to account for the flow of vehicles
478 (Barrigón-Morillas et al., 2005). This gave values for the explanation of the variability of
479 noise of around 65%. In another study, Rey Gozalo et al. found that 85% of the sound
480 level variability was explained by the logarithm of traffic flow when traffic flows were
481 recorded controlling that road traffic was the main source of sound and using the
482 categorisation method to classify street types (Rey Gozalo et al., 2019). Other researchers
483 have considered multivariate models: for example, Wang et al. developed a multivariate
484 model for estimating the average annual $L_{eq,24h}$ that included up to 10 variables (the road
485 width, the annual average total traffic flow rates for light vehicles, heavy vehicles and
486 motorcycles, and six land use variables), and reported values for the variability
487 explanation of 75% (Wang et al., 2016).

488 From the data in Table 2, the percentage of noise monitoring stations explaining certain
489 percentages of the variability of $L_{Aeq,1h}$ by $MHFR(j)$ can be calculated. As shown in Fig.
490 5 for case C4, the results show that 94% (77%) of the 31 noise monitoring stations explain
491 at least 50% (60%) of the variability in $L_{Aeq,1h}$, when the anomalous data are included
492 (excluded). It is also noteworthy that 36% of the stations reach at least 70% of the

493 explanation of the variability of $L_{Aeq,1h}$ only from a variable related to vehicle flow such
494 as $MHFR(j)$.

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496 Fig. 5. Percentage of noise monitoring stations explaining certain percentages of the
497 variability of $L_{Aeq,1h}$ from $MHFR(j)$ for case C4.

498 The lowest value of the coefficient of determination was found for station 3 (Plaza del
499 Carmen), as shown in Table 2, possibly because this noise station was located in a square
500 with restricted motor vehicle traffic and significant commercial activity. The relatively
501 small effect of road traffic flow on the sound levels measured at this point therefore seems
502 to be clear. Another point with a low value for the coefficient of determination was station
503 18 (Casa de Campo), which was located in a large green area where the closest sound
504 sources were people and nature, and where the nearest major road sections (A5 and M30)
505 were approximately 1.2 and 1.5 km away. These results seem to support the ability of the
506 proposed variable to analyse the relative importance of traffic with respect to other sound

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507 sources. Many other circumstances can be indicated to understand the variability of the
508 values found for the coefficients of determination in the rest of the measurement points
509 studied. Anomalous events, circumstances specific for each measurement point or area,
510 the relative importance of road traffic in environmental noise, noise from other sources
511 such as pedestrians, etc., may have influenced $L_{Aeq,1h}$ and affected the correlation between
512 noise and hourly traffic flow. This opens up the possibility that subsequent studies could
513 focus on a specific analysis of the sound sources present at each of the measurement
514 points and the linear relationships found. It should not be forgotten that, due to the
515 temporal precision of the new defined variable, these studies can be carried out with a
516 temporal precision of one hour. It should also be noted that given the applicability of the
517 variable $MHFR(j)$ to the whole city, specific traffic flow measurements at each point of
518 interest would not be necessary to carry out a study of the relative importance of road
519 traffic with respect to other sound sources.

520 A comparison of the results presented in this study with those of previous studies should
521 take into account several aspects of interest. In previous studies, sound level
522 measurements have corresponded to samples of short duration, which have been used on
523 occasion to estimate values of long duration (Wang et al., 2016). This represents an
524 essential difference from this study, as studies based on short samples usually control for
525 both anomalous sound events (corresponding to sound sources other than or specific to
526 road traffic) and meteorological conditions. Furthermore, in multivariate models, in
527 addition to the obvious fact that many variables are considered, it must be remembered
528 that these variables usually differentiate between specific characteristics of the traffic
529 itself, such as the type of vehicle.

530 It must be indicated that it is reasonable to believe that the results found in this work offer
531 the possibility that the proposed variable could be useful for the study of other pollutants

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532 related to road traffic that could affect people or the environment. It is clear that different
533 factors, such as the type of street, land uses, proximity to different infrastructures, distance
534 to work or service centres, etc., can affect the structure of road traffic flow at different
535 times of the day or even on different days of the year. Therefore, by using a single variable
536 to describe the hour-by-hour structure of urban traffic for a year, specific details of certain
537 points or areas of the city may be lost. These details may, in some cases, be necessary for
538 an accurate study of what happens at those points. This is true whether we want to
539 describe the flow of road traffic or whether we are studying its ability to explain a traffic-
540 related environmental pollution variable, such as urban noise. What has been found in the
541 study is that, despite the existence of this spatial variability in the hourly structure of road
542 traffic, the variable $MHFR(j)$ can be used to describe the flow variability of road traffic
543 in a large city and also the variability of one of the most important pollutants related to
544 this flow, urban noise.

545 4. CONCLUSIONS

546 The results presented here indicate that, by using a single variable, obtained from urban
547 networks for monitoring road traffic flows, it is possible to know the temporal and spatial
548 variation in vehicle flows throughout the city. This offers the possibility of studying other
549 variables that are directly influenced by road traffic, such as noise pollution or certain
550 types of air pollutants, with a temporal precision of one hour.

551 To test the quality and usefulness of the $MHFR(j)$ variable, a study has been developed to
552 analyse the ability of this variable to explain the variability of urban noise for each of the
553 31 stations of the noise monitoring network spread throughout the city. Highly statistically
554 significant positive correlations ($p < 0.001$) were found between the noise indicator $L_{Aeq,1h}$
555 and $MHFR(j)$ at the 31 noise monitoring stations. Negligible differences in the

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556 explanation of the noise level variability by the *MHFR(j)* variable were found when the
557 anomalies of the flow data were included or excluded, and only small differences were
558 found when the anomalies in the sound level data were included or excluded. These
559 results reinforce the conclusion on the stability of the proposed variable.

560 Consequently, it is demonstrated that the matrix variable *MHFR(j)* can explain in a
561 statistically significant way the hourly variability of sound levels throughout the year at
562 all measurement stations in the city of Madrid. These findings open up a wide field of
563 study: investigating other variables that measure the effects of traffic on people or the
564 environment and that may be specifically influenced by the hourly variability of traffic;
565 detecting differences in flow structure according to street type, neighborhood, or land use;
566 analysing the relationship of this variable with annual temperature variability, urban
567 planning, noise sources, etc.

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Declaration of interests

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Author contributions statement

Juan Miguel Barrigón Morillas: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Validation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Resources, Data Curation, Writing – Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **David Montes González:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Original Draft, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization. **Guillermo Rey-Gozalo:** Methodology, Software, Formal analysis, Investigation, Data Curation, Writing - Review & Editing, Visualization.